

A Class of Continuous Linear Multistep Method for Solving Second Order Ordinary Differential Equations

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Abstract:- In this research work, a Class of Continuous 4-Step Method (CCSM) for solving second order ordinary differential equations is provided. The step size of the approximate solution affects the coefficients of the developed approach. As a by-product of the continuous technique, a discrete second derivatives method is obtained from the continuous method. At any stage in collocation, the primary predictor needed for the implicit method assessment is of the same order as the method. The stability, consistency, and convergence aspects of the method were discussed and used to solve linear and non-linear problems in order to demonstrate its applicability and efficiency.

Keywords:- Interpolation, Collocation, Ordinary Differential Equation, Predictor-Corrector.

I. INTRODUCTION

The numerical solution of the second order initial value problem in form (1) is taken into consideration.

$$y'' = f(x, y, y'); y(a) = y_0; y'(a) = y_1 \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) is the result of many physical phenomena, particularly those in engineering, such as fluid dynamics, electrical circuits, satellite motion, and others. Researchers [9], [11], [18], and others had mentioned using this approach. Most of the time, (1) can be solved by reducing it to the equivalent system of the first ordinary differential equation, which may then be solved numerically according to the application. Despite the efficacy of the strategy, [2] asserts that there are certain drawbacks. These drawbacks include being uneconomical in terms of implementation costs, increasing the amount of computation required and the amount of time wasted by computers, growing the size of the resulting systems of equations that must be solved, and lacking any additional details regarding a particular ordinary differential equation. If the given system of equations cannot be explicitly solved with regard to the highest order derivative, the method is worthless. A strategy for directly resolving the system of higher order ordinary differential equations has been put out by [5], [11], [12], [13], and others. According to [2] and [5], the continuous linear multistep method offers more advantages. It offers a more accurate estimation of the

error, simplifies the coefficient for use in subsequent analyses at various places, and assures that the solution is approximatively simple at all interior points of the integration interval. A few eminent academics who have made substantial contributions to this field of study are [18], [9], [20], [1], and [5]. This study is driven by the need to develop a direct method based on collocation and interpolation to construct a continuous 4-step method for the solution of second order ordinary differential equations in order to solve the inadequacies of the existing methodologies. In this work, power series was used as the basis function to create the continuous hybrid linear multistep that was developed for the solution of problem (1).

II. DERIVATION OF THE METHOD

CCSM is obtained by approximating the exact solution $y(x)$ by searching the solution $y(x,)$, which provides a discrete method as a by-product. The method has the form

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{(c+i)-1} a_j x^j \quad (2)$$

will be employed as a basis function to approximate the solution of second order initial value problems of the type (3), (2)'s second derivative is given as:

$$y''(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{(c+i)-1} j(j-1)a_j x^{j-2} \quad (3)$$

Through interpolation of (2) at $x = x_{n+1}$ and $x_{n+\frac{1}{2}}$, collocation of (3) at $x = x_{n+i}, i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$ to obtain $k+3$ system of equation, where k is the step number

$$y(x_{n+j}) = y_{n+j}, j = 0(4)$$

$$y(x_{n+j}, u) = f_{n+j}, j = 0(4)k \quad (5)$$

Equations (2) and (3) result in an equation system that is solved by the Gaussian elimination method to yield the parameter a_j 's. By entering the values of a_j 's into equation (2), the CCSM is stated in the form after some algebraic manipulation.

$$y_{n+4} = \alpha_1 y_{n+1} + \alpha_{\frac{1}{2}} y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} + h^2(\beta_0 f_n + \beta_1 f_{n+1} + \beta_2 f_{n+2} + \beta_3 f_{n+3} + \beta_4 f_{n+4}) \quad (6)$$

The coefficients are obtained as follows using the transformation

$$t = \frac{x - x_{n+k-1}}{h}$$

$$\frac{dt}{dx} = \frac{1}{h}$$

The coefficients of y_{n+j} and f_{n+j} are obtained as:

$$\alpha_1 = 2t + 5 \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha_{\frac{1}{2}} = -2t - 4 \quad (8)$$

$$\beta_0 = \frac{h^2}{23040} (32t^6 + 96t^5 - 80t^4 - 320t^3 + 113t - 30) \quad (9)$$

$$\beta_1 = -\frac{h^2}{2880} (16t^6 + 72t^5 - 40t^4 - 240t^3 - 1875t - 3750) \quad (10)$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{h^2}{3840} (32t^6 + 192t^5 + 80t^4 - 960t^3 + 4647t + 4430) \quad (11)$$

$$\beta_3 = -\frac{h^2}{180} (t + 2) \left(t + \frac{5}{2}\right) \left(t^4 + 3t^3 - 6t^2 - 13t - \frac{3}{2}\right) \quad (12)$$

$$\beta_4 = \frac{h^2}{23040} (32t^6 + 288t^5 + 880t^4 + 960t^3 - 339t + 90) \quad (13)$$

The first derivatives of equation (7 - 13) are as follows

$$\alpha'_1 = 2 \quad (14)$$

$$\alpha'_{\frac{1}{2}} = -2 \quad (15)$$

$$\beta'_0 = \frac{h^2}{23040} (192t^5 + 480t^4 - 320t^3 - 960t^2 + 113) \quad (16)$$

$$\beta'_1 = -\frac{h^2}{2880} (96t^5 + 360t^4 - 160t^3 - 720t^2 - 1875) \quad (17)$$

$$\beta'_2 = \frac{h^2}{3840} (192t^5 + 960t^4 + 320t^3 - 2880t^2 + 4647) \quad (18)$$

$$\beta'_3 = -\frac{h^2}{180} \left(t + \frac{5}{2}\right) (t^4 + 3t^3 - 6t^2 - 13t - \frac{3}{2}) - \frac{h^2}{180} (t + 2) (t^4 + 3t^3 - 6t^2 - 13t - \frac{3}{2}) - \frac{h^2}{180} (t + 2) \left(t + \frac{5}{2}\right) (4t^3 + 9t^2 - 12t - 13) \quad (19)$$

$$\beta'_4 = \frac{h^2}{23040} (192t^5 + 1440t^4 + 3520t^3 + 2880t^2 - 339) \quad (20)$$

Evaluating (3.28 – 3.34) at $t = 1$, yields the discrete 4-step method

$$y_{n+4} = \frac{h^2}{7680} (-63 f_n + 15512 f_{n+1} + 16842 f_{n+2} + 7392 f_{n+3} + 637 f_{n+4}) + 7 y_{n+1} - 6 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tag{21}$$

with first derivative

$$y'_{n+4} = \frac{1}{23040h} (-495 f_n + 18392 f_{n+1} + 19434 f_{n+2} + 29856 f_{n+3} + 7693 f_{n+4}) + 46080 y_{n+1} - 46080 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tag{22}$$

The predictor of the method and its derivatives are obtained as

$$y_{n+4} = \frac{h^2}{9600} (5495 f_n + 41685 f_{n+1} + 9905 f_{n+2} + 13699 f_{n+3} - 20384 f_{n+\frac{1}{2}}) + 7 y_{n+1} - 6 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tag{23}$$

$$y'_{n+4} = \frac{h^2}{28800h} (66695 f_n + 292245 f_{n+1} - 110335 f_{n+2} + 91171 f_{n+3} - 246176 f_{n+\frac{1}{2}}) + 57600 y_{n+1} - 57600 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tag{24}$$

III. ANALYSIS OF THE METHOD

Basic properties of the main method was analyzed to establish their validity. These properties namely: order, error constant, stability and consistency was obtained in this chapter. In what follows, a brief introduction of these properties are made for a better comprehension of the chapter.

➤ *Order and Error Constant of the Method*

Let the linear Operator defined on the method be $[y(x); h]$,

$$[y(x); h] = C_0 y(x) + C_1 h y'(x) + \dots + C_p h^p y^{(p)}(x) + C_{p+1} h^{p+1} y^{(p+1)}(x) + C_{p+2} h^{p+2} y^{(p+2)}(x) + \dots \quad C_0 = C_1 = C_2 = \dots = C_{p+3} = 0, C_{p+4} \neq 0$$

- *Definition* : The term C_{p+4} is called the error constant and it implies that the local truncation error is given as

$$T_{n+k} = C_{p+4} h^{p+4} y^{(p+4)}(x) + O(h^{p+5})$$

- *Order and Error Constant for the Main Method*

The derivation of the order and error constant of the method are as follows:

$$y_{n+4} = \frac{h^2}{7680} (-63 f_n + 15512 f_{n+1} + 16842 f_{n+2} + 7392 f_{n+3} + 637 f_{n+4}) + 7 y_{n+1} - 6 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}}$$

With first derivative

$$y'_{n+4} = \frac{1}{23040h} (-495 f_n + 18392 f_{n+1} + 19434 f_{n+2} + 29856 f_{n+3} + 7693 f_{n+4}) + 46080 y_{n+1} - 46080 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}}$$

Expanding the method and its derivatives by Taylor series and combining coefficients of like terms in h^n give

$$c_0 = c_1 = c_2 = c_3 = c_4 = c_5 = c_6 = 0, c_7 = \frac{-139}{15360} = -0.0090495$$

Hence the method is of order 5 and the error constant is -0.0090495 while the error for the derivative is -2.453717138

$$y_{n+4} = \frac{h^2}{9600} (5495 f_n + 41685 f_{n+1} + 9905 f_{n+2} + 13699 f_{n+3} - 20384 f_{n+\frac{1}{2}}) + 7 y_{n+1} - 6 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tag{25}$$

$$y'_{n+4} = \frac{h^2}{28800h} (66695 f_n + 292245 f_{n+1} - 110335 f_{n+2} + 91171 f_{n+3} - 246176 f_{n+\frac{1}{2}}) + 57600 y_{n+1} - 57600 y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} \tag{26}$$

Combining the coefficients of similar terms in h^n and extending the technique and its derivatives by the Taylor series results in $c_0 = c_1 = c_2 = c_3 = c_4 = c_5 = c_6 = 0$, $c_7 = \frac{941}{19200} = 0.0490104$. Hence the first derivative of the main predictor is $\frac{941}{19200} = 0.0490104$ while the error for the derivative is $\frac{-895417}{403200} = -2.2207762$

➤ Consistency

The linear multi step technique is said to be consistent if it satisfies the following conditions

- the order $p \geq 1$
- $\sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j = 0$
- $\rho(1) = \rho'(1) = 0$
- $\rho^{ii}(1) = 2!\sigma(1)$
- Consistency of the Method

$$y_{n+4} + 6y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} - 7y_{n+1} = \frac{h^2}{7680} (-63f_n + 15512f_{n+1} + 16842f_{n+2} + 7392f_{n+3} + 637f_{n+4}) \tag{27}$$

✓ Condition (1) is satisfied since $P = 5$

$$\alpha_1 = -7; \alpha_{\frac{1}{2}} = 6; \alpha_4 = 1$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j = \alpha_1 + \alpha_{\frac{1}{2}} + \alpha_4 = -7 + 6 + 1 = 0$$

✓ Condition (2) is satisfied since

$$\sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j = 0$$

Here, $\rho(r)$ is the first characteristic polynomial while $\sigma(r)$ is the second characteristics polynomial $\rho(r) = r^4 + 6r^{\frac{1}{2}} - 7r$

$$\sigma(r) = \frac{1}{7680} (-63 + 15512r + 16842r^2 + 7392r^3 + 637r^4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(1) &= r^4 + 6r^{\frac{1}{2}} - 7r = 0, \text{ when } r = 1 \\ \rho'(r) &= 4r^3 + \frac{3}{\sqrt{r}} - 7 \\ \rho'(1) &= 4r^3 + \frac{3}{\sqrt{r}} - 7 = 0, \text{ when } r = 1 \end{aligned}$$

✓ Condition (3) is satisfied since $\rho''(1) = 0$

$$\rho''(r) = 12r^2 - \frac{3}{2r^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \frac{21}{2}, \text{ when } r = 1$$

$$\sigma(r) = \frac{1}{7680} (-63 + 15512r + 16842r^2 + 7392r^3 + 637r^4)$$

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$$2!\sigma(r) = \frac{2!}{7680} (-63 + 15512r + 16842r^2 + 7392r^3 + 637r^4) = \frac{21}{2}$$

When $r = 1$

$$\rho''(r) = 2!\sigma(r) = \frac{21}{2}$$

- ✓ Condition (4) is satisfied since $\rho''(1) = 2!\sigma(1)$
Hence, the four condition of consistency are satisfied.

➤ *Zero - Stability of the Method*

$$y_{n+4} = 7y_{n+1} - 6y_{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{h^2}{7680} (-63f_n + 15512f_{n+1} + 16842f_{n+2} + 7392f_{n+3} + 637f_{n+4})$$

The first characteristic polynomial according to the definition

$$\rho(r) = r^4 + 6r^{\frac{1}{2}} - 7r$$

On solving $\rho(r)$ gives

$$r = 0, 1$$

Which satisfies $|R_j| \geq 1, j = 1, \dots, k$, the multiplicity is simple and that the roots are in the unit circle. The approach is hence zero stable.

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Introduction*

This chapter talked about how the developed method was put into practice. Furthermore, some numerical examples of nonlinear and linear value problems of general second order ordinary differential equations are used to test the effectiveness of the method. The absolute error of the approximate solution are computed and compared with results from existing methods. The results from the method are also discussed here.

➤ *Numerical Examples*

To test the viability of the created method, we give some numerical experiments with the four challenges below. The 4-Step Method was used to solve the following test issues.

- *Problem 1*

$$y'' = 100y; y(0) = 1, y'(0) = -10, h = 0.01 \text{ exact solution: } y(x) = \exp(-10x)$$

- *Problem 2*

$$y'' = y'; y(0) = 0; y'(0) = -1, h = 0.1 \text{ exact solution: } y(x) = 1 - \exp(x)$$

- *Problem 3*

A stamping machine applies hammering forces on metal sheets by a die attached to the plunger which moves vertically up and down by a fly wheel makes the impact force on the metal sheet and therefore the supporting base, intermittent and cyclic. The bearing base on which the metal sheet is situated has a mass, $M = 2000\text{kg}$. The force acting on the base follows a function: $f(t) = 2000\sin(10t)$, in which t =time in seconds. The base is supported by an elastic pad with an equivalent spring constant $k = 2 * 10^5\text{N/M}$. Determine the differential equation for the instantaneous position of the base $y(t)$ if the base is initially depressed down by an amount 0.1m .

- ✓ *Solution:* The mass-spring system above is modeled as differential equation:

The Bearing base mass = 2000kg

Spring constant $k = 2 * 10^5\text{N/M}$

Force (ma) on the metal sheet = $m \frac{d^2y}{dt^2} = my''$

i.e. $ma = my'' = 2000\sin(10t)$; where $a = y''$

Initial conditions on the system are

$$y(t_0) = y_0; \frac{dy}{dt}|_{t=0} = y'(t_0) = y'(0); t_0 = 0, y'_0 = 0.1$$

Therefore, the governing equation for the instantaneous position of the base $y(t)$ is given by

$$My'' + ky = F(t); y(t_0) = y_0, y'(t_0) = y_0'$$

✓ Theoretical solution: $y(t) = \frac{1}{10}\cos 10t + \frac{1}{200}\sin 10t - \frac{t}{20}\cos 10t$

• Problem 4

$$y'' + y = 0; y(0) = 0; y'(0) = 1, h = 0.025 \text{ exact solution: } y = \sin(x)$$

➤ Numerical Results

Table 1 Result of problem 1, for $h=0.01$

X	Exact solution	Computed Solution	Error in the new method	Error in [1]
0.01	0.904837418035960	0.904837419100000	$1.064040e - 09$	$1.157e - 07$
0.02	0.818730753077982	0.818730755100000	$2.022018e - 09$	$3.658e - 07$
0.03	0.740818220681718	0.740818222800000	$2.118282e - 09$	$6.051e - 07$
0.04	0.670320046035639	0.670320049600000	$3.564361e - 09$	$8.502e - 07$
0.05	0.606530659712633	0.606530663901465	$4.188832e - 09$	$1.104e - 06$
0.06	0.548811636094026	0.548811640871017	$4.776991e - 09$	$1.369e - 06$
0.07	0.496585303791410	0.496585308613180	$4.821770e - 09$	$1.450e - 06$
0.08	0.449328964117222	0.44932896922628	$5.805406e - 09$	$1.597e - 06$
0.09	0.406569659740599	0.406569666013090	$6.272491e - 09$	$1.763e - 06$
0.10	0.367879441171442	0.367879447921353	$6.749911e - 09$	$1.946e - 06$

Fig 1 Efficiency Curve for Problem 1 Compared with Error in [1]

Table 2 Result of Problem 2, for $h=0.1$

X	Exact Solution	Computed Solution	Error in the new method	Error in [14]
0.2	-0.22140275816017	-0.221402754800000	$3.3601700e - 09$	$8.17176e - 07$
0.3	-0.34985880757600	-0.349858801900000	$5.6760000e - 09$	$3.10356e - 06$
0.4	-0.49182469764127	-0.491824690000000	$7.6412700e - 09$	$6.56957e - 06$
0.5	-0.64872127070013	-0.648721260202993	$1.0497137e - 08$	$1.14380e - 05$
0.6	-0.82211880039051	-0.822118786044656	$1.4345854e - 08$	$1.79656e - 05$
0.7	-1.01375270747048	-1.013752688688240	$1.8782240e - 08$	$2.64474e - 05$
0.8	-1.22554092849247	-1.225540905693600	$2.2798870e - 08$	$3.72222e - 05$
0.9	-1.45960311115695	-1.459603082898740	$2.8258210e - 08$	$5.06788e - 05$
1.0	-1.71828182845905	-1.718281793134250	$3.5324800e - 08$	$6.72615e - 05$

Fig 2 Efficiency Curve for Problem 2 Compared with Error in [14]

Table 3 Result of Problem 3, for h=0.0001

X	Exact Solution	Computed Solution	Error in the new method	Error in [15]
0.1	0.999999500016710	0.999999000016667	$5.49999900e - 10$	$1.541367e - 09$
0.2	0.999998000134000	0.999996000133333	$2.09999970e - 09$	$2.976799e - 09$
0.3	0.999995499778380	0.999991000449999	$4.64993300e - 09$	$1.032860e - 09$
0.4	0.999991999477330	0.999984000466663	$8.16984030e - 09$	$2.447733e - 09$
0.5	0.999987502109373	0.999975001889056	$1.27755651e - 08$	$4.069112e - 09$
0.6	0.999982003653984	0.999964003828369	$1.83811325e - 08$	$1.337372e - 08$
0.7	0.999975497241720	0.999951006433303	$2.49858426e - 08$	$1.711910e - 08$
0.8	0.999967995904010	0.999936009219869	$3.25609866e - 08$	$1.388529e - 08$
0.9	0.999959512423277	0.999919013807462	$4.12234072e - 08$	$1.833084e - 08$
1.0	0.999950017083162	0.999900019390904	$5.08845536e - 08$	$4.286197e - 08$

Fig 3 Efficiency Curve for Problem 3 Compared with Error in [15]

Table 4 Result of Problem 4, for h=0.025

X	Exact Solution	Computed Solution	Error in the new method	Error in [20]
0.01	0.0249973959147123	0.024997395910000	$4.7123e - 12$	$1.50000e - 08$
0.02	0.0499791692706783	0.049979169270000	$6.7830e - 13$	$2.46000e - 07$
0.03	0.0749297072727423	0.074929707270000	$2.7423e - 12$	$1.37100e - 06$
0.04	0.0998334166468282	0.099833416640000	$6.8282e - 12$	$2.65200e - 06$
0.05	0.1246747333852280	0.124674733374188	$1.1040e - 11$	$1.28450e - 05$
0.06	0.1494381324735990	0.149438132462708	$1.0891e - 11$	$4.27070e - 05$
0.07	0.1741081375935960	0.174108137576993	$1.6603e - 11$	$8.31840e - 05$
0.08	0.1986693307950610	0.198669330735944	$5.9117e - 11$	$2.60181e - 04$

Fig 4 Efficiency Curve for Problem 4 Compared with Error in [20]

V. DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

In this paper, we have considered four numerical examples to test the efficiency of our method. The effect of decreasing mesh size was tested and the results showed that the smaller the mesh size, the better the accuracy. The new method gave better approximation because the proposed method requires self-starting.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

➤ Conclusion

In this study, a class of continuous 4-step methods for second order ordinary differential equations are presented. A collocation and interpolation strategy was used to create the method. Predictor-corrector mode was used to implement the derived approach. It was found that our technique converges, zero stable, and is consistent. A few current methods have been compared to the results. The method performed better than the current methods, as shown by the comparison of errors.

➤ Recommendation

This paper considered a class of continuous 4-step method for solving second order ordinary differential equations. The method had been tested for usability and recommended that the method be used for solving second order ordinary differential equations for efficiency and accuracy.

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